

Bromination of substituted methylcoumarins with N-bromo-succinimide.

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Manuscript received 12 January 1974; accepted 11 July 1974.

Bromination of 7-methoxy-5-methylcoumarin, 5-methoxy-4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin and 7-methoxy-4-, 8-dimethylcoumarin with N-bromosuccinimide gave 7-methoxy-5-bromomethylcoumarin, 5-methoxy-4-methyl-7-bromomethylcoumarin and 7-methoxy-4-methyl-8-bromomethylcoumarin, while 5-hydroxy-4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin gave 5-hydroxy-6-bromo-4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin under similar conditions.

MOLHO and Mentzer¹ carried out the bromination of 3-methylcoumarin and 7-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin with N-bromosuccinimide and obtained 3-bromomethylcoumarin and 7-methoxy-3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin. The action of N-bromosuccinimide on methylcoumarins has been extensively studied by Lecocq and Buu-Hoi^{2,3}. They observed that N-bromosuccinimide reacts only with the methyl group in the benzene ring but not with the methyl group in the heterocyclic ring. Thus they prepared 4-methyl-7-bromomethyl; 4-methyl-6-bromomethyl and 6-bromomethylcoumarin from 4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin; 4,6-dimethylcoumarin and 6-methylcoumarin respectively, while 4-methylcoumarin gave 3-bromo-4-methylcoumarin.

We required large quantities of differently substituted bromomethylcoumarin derivatives for the synthesis of nitrogen mustards to study their structure activity relationship⁴. We report here the bromination of some methylcoumarins with N-bromosuccinimide.

Bromination of 5-hydroxy-4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin (Ia) with N-bromosuccinimide, gave a product with m.p. 217°. This on reduction with zinc and acetic acid gave the original bromo compound back indicating that no bromomethyl derivative has been formed instead bromine must have entered 3,6 or 8-position of the coumarin ring. Lele and Sethna⁵ carried out the bromination of 5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin by bromine in acetic acid and obtained 5-hydroxy-8-bromo-4,7-dimethylcoumarin m.p. 257°-58° (decomp.). Desai and Gaitonde⁶ reported that the bromination of 5-hydroxy-4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin in acetic acid gave a product m. p. 217°, to which they assigned the structure of 5-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin which was later on proved to be incorrect by Lele and Sethna⁵. Hence the product was methylated and subjected to hydrolysis with 10% sodium carbonate solution. It gave the original product back indicating that bromine is not in the 3-position but must be in the 6-position. This structure (Ib) was confirmed by comparing it with an authentic sample of 5-hydroxy-6-bromo-4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin prepared by condensing 4-bromo-2-hydroxyacetophenone with ethyl acetoacetate according to Chakravarti and Mukerjee⁷.

7-Methoxy-5-methylcoumarin; 5-methoxy-4-, 7-dimethylcoumarin and 7-methoxy-4-, 8-dimethylcoumarin on bromination with N-bromosuccinimide in dry benzene gave 7-methoxy-5-bromomethylcoumarin (IIa), 5-methoxy-4-methyl-7-bromomethylcoumarin (IIb) and 7-methoxy-4-methyl-8-bromomethylcoumarin (IIc) respectively. This bromomethylcoumarin derivatives on reduction with zinc and acetic acid gave original methylcoumarins back. The above methoxycoumarins were prepared by the methylation of corresponding hydroxy coumarin derivatives.

(a) x = H
(b) X = Br

(a) R = R₃ = H; R₁ = CH₂Br;
R₂ = OCH₃
(b) R = CH₃; R₁ = OCH₃;
R₂ = CH₂Br; R₃ = H
(c) R = CH₃; R₁ = H;
R₂ = OCH₃;
R₃ = CH₂Br

Experimental

5-Hydroxy-6-bromo-4-, 7 dimethylcoumarin (Ib): A suspension of 5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin (1 g.); N-bromosuccinimide (1, g.) and benzoyl peroxide (50 mg) in dry benzene (50 ml) was refluxed on a water bath for 8hrs. Clear solution was evaporated at room temperature and pale yellow residue which left was treated with cold water, filtered, dried crystallised several times with acetic acid and finally from benzene. Yield 0.4 g. m p. 217°. (Found: C, 49.18; H, 3.23; Br, 29.68%. Calc. for C₁₁H₉BrO₃: C, 49.07; H, 3.35; Br, 29.73%.) Mixed m.p. with the authentic sample⁷ was not depressed.

5-Methoxy-6-bromo-4,7-dimethylcoumarin : A mixture of 7-hydroxy-6-bromo-4, 7-dimethylcoumarin (0.5 g.); freshly fused potassium carbonate (1 g.) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) in dry acetone (20 ml.) was refluxed on a water bath for 7 hrs. Solvent was evaporated, treated with dilute alkali, filtered and crystallised from acetic acid. Yield 0.45 g. m.p. 161°-62°. (Found : C, 50.52 ; H, 3.60 ; Br, 28.52%. Calculated for $C_{12}H_{11}BrO_3$: C, 50.88 ; H, 3.88 ; Br, 28.27%).

7-Methoxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin : A mixture of 7-hydroxy, 4,8-dimethylcoumarin was methylated as above. The product was crystallised from benzene as colourless needles, m.p. 158°-61°. (Found : C, 70.50 ; H, 5.57%. Calculated for $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$: C, 70.59 ; H, 5.88%).

General procedure for the reduction of bromomethylcoumarin derivatives : A mixture of bromomethylcoumarin (0.5 g.) derivative was refluxed with zinc dust (1 g.) and distilled acetic acid (10 ml.) for 3hrs. It was filtered hot and concentrated to half its volume. On keeping, the products separated and crystallised from alcohol. Mixed m. p. s with the original methylcoumarins were not depressed.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. S. Sethna for his keen interest in the work and to Dr. S. S. Lele for elemental analysis of the samples.

TABLE I

No.	Bromomethyl coumarins	Compound No.	Yield (gm.)	M. P.	Formula	Carbon %		Hydrogen %		Bromine %	
						Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
1.	7-Methoxy-5-bromo-methyl-coumarin	IIa	0.6	164°	$C_{11}H_9BrO_3$	—	—	—	—	29.56	29.74
2.	5-Methoxy-4-methyl 7-bromo-methyl-coumarin	IIb	0.5	210°	$C_{12}H_{11}BrO_3$	50.66	50.88	3.43	3.88	28.08	28.27
3.	7-Methoxy-4-methyl-8-bromo-methyl-coumarin	IIc	0.5	210-11°	$C_{12}H_{11}BrO_3$	—	—	—	—	28.61	28.27

General procedure for the bromination of methylcoumarins : N-bromosuccinimide (0.9 g.) in dry benzene (15 ml) was mixed with methylcoumarin derivative (1 g.) in dry benzene (10 ml). Benzoyl peroxide (50 mg.) was then added. After refluxing the reaction mixture on a water bath for 8 hrs. the solvent was evaporated at room temperature and pale yellow residue was washed with water to remove any unreacted N-bromosuccinimide. Crude product was chromatographed over silica gel and eluted with benzene-petroleum ether mixture (80 : 20). Evaporation of the solvent gave products, which were crystallised several times with acetic acid and finally from benzene as colourless shining crystals (Table I).

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